

Determinants of Health Challenges and Healthcare Services Among Older People

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Abstract

Old age should be a leisure period, but for some older adults, it is the opposite due to lack of adequate care which has compelled some of them to beg at public events and parks or work at odd places. In underdeveloped nations like Nigeria, governmental and public plans seldom address socio-economic and gender concerns that affect older adults' health. However, findings from secondary data and online libraries affirmed that older adults lack essential health, medical, and social care, which are determined by the political economy of a country and the expenses associated with such provisions. Though elders are crucial to society, dishearteningly, they have been consciously and unconsciously abandoned in Nigeria compared to wealthy nations where they get adequate healthcare services, leaving them with no hope for tomorrow. Youngsters find it difficult to acquire suitable jobs after education, dashing the hopes of older adults who have invested in them to receive support when ageing. Poor health among older adults is worrisome since they are often neglected and exposed to health challenges such as malnourishment and other old age-related issues, reducing their pleasant social activities. The paper also found that poverty, lifestyle, marital status, and gender, among others, determine quality health among the elderly and concluded that such determinants worsen healthcare services for older adults. Maintaining healthy behaviours throughout life, mainly eating a balanced diet, engaging in regular physical and mental activity and capacity, delaying care dependency and refraining from tobacco use,

are found to be significant to optimal health conditions among older adults. The paper concludes that addressing social challenges faced by young people will contribute significantly to achieving good health in old age.

Keywords: Ageing, aged, health, health determinants, healthcare services, older adults

Introduction

Improving older adults' health requires focusing attention on their social conditions, which could increase life expectancy and extend the human life span. Older age is a biological phenomenon having medical, psychological, economic, social, and cultural traits and idiosyncrasies. Longer life span is a product of the modern era, a feature of the developed society and one of the United Nations' most significant 21st-century focus. Though adding years to one's life does not guarantee a high quality of life, however, ageing often brings biological health challenges such as impaired sight and hearing, reduced organ functionality, loss of mobility or autonomy, as well as social declines, which is older adults' withdrawal from professional life and society. Older adults are marginalised, neglected, often abused and faced with social death before biological death (Fonta *et al.*, 2017). Ageing is a realistic concept that has been linked to dementia, arthritis, heart disease and diabetes (World Health Organisation, 2021). Hence, science and experts must therefore offer timely and appropriate responses on individual, societal, and global levels.

Nigeria's extended family has traditionally cared for the elderly by providing a lot of support through help from relatives, friends and children

(Okumagba, 2011). Large families in Nigeria were motivated by the need for elderly age security from children. Therefore, the decline in family support networks, poor economy, increased unemployment, underemployment and inflation have deprived many families, particularly children, to adequate care for older parents. In rural sub-Saharan Africa, urbanisation often separates young people from their families, who are agents of traditional education and socialisation. According to Gesinde *et al.* (2011), elderly Nigerians most times face insufficient customary family support, poor access to healthcare, social exclusion, and poor social security. These challenges have been triggered by the exposure of youngsters to the HIV/AIDS epidemic and the nonchalant attitudes of the government towards the care of the elderly, which have resulted in the early deaths and incapacity of the young and left the elderly with less support and the burdens of caring for orphans.

Mudiare (2013) observed that most elderly Nigerians do not work, experience increased dependency, isolation, loneliness, and bereavement due to spouse and friend losses and more vulnerability to poverty and disease, and are usually left behind due to declining physical ability. Similarly, WHO (2021) revealed that

older adults are more likely to have reduced mobility due to muscular-skeletal changes and certain diseases such as cataracts, arthritis, heart disease and diabetes. The elderly may occasionally be excluded from social events, which could negatively impact their health. These can cause them to become confused and senile and prohibit them from receiving food, housing, medical, emotional support, personal hygiene, and environmental health benefits. Access to high-quality healthcare for the elderly is hampered by cost and location; therefore, many older adults get exploited by herbalists and traditional healers who mostly render services to them. Even though some senior citizens self-medicate to keep themselves healthy, they still face difficulties in accessing quality healthcare services that are crucial for optimal health. Against this background, this paper explores the determinants of health challenges and healthcare services among the aged population in Nigeria.

Conceptual Review

The Concept of Ageing

The term ageing has gained lots of attention over the years as the population of older adults keeps rising. According to Hagberg (2008), ageing is defined as a periodic change in human life, which means man and the conditions he is subjected to change as time passes constantly. Plank *et al.* (2011) see ageing as a process that cannot be avoided, a slow process that could mean gradual degeneration in the structure and vital organs of both humans and animals, which happen as time passes. This degeneration is not affiliated with diseases or other types of profound disabilities,

but with time, it may eventually lead to death. Ageing is not seen as an illness but rather as being associated with independent risk-factor of disability and death. When ageing sets in, the standard functionality of the body system begins to decline, and this marks the beginning of another life. The new life, referred to as ageing, becomes an important study area for researchers. According to Plank *et al.* (2011), present investigations are directed towards ageing, age-related changes and their impact on health. In this paper, ageing is described as an inevitable change, including social, economic, physical, psychological or cultural, that people experience as they grow old.

The Concept of Old Age

There is no specific age to describe old age. However, it is a period in a person's life when the body's system diminishes in functionality. It has been challenging to set a certain age for old age; different ages are considered old in different countries. According to Robertson (1996), in his discussion on 'what is old age?', the retirement age for judges in the United Kingdom is 70, and the pension age for women is raised to 65. A study carried out in Sweden sets old age at 76, while the study conducted in Finland about depression among older adults considers the category of people with age 60 years and above as the old age class. The elderly could be referred to as people that are older than 60 years; some people set it to be 65, while some authors raised it to be a person at 70 years of age or older (Kotkamp-Mothes *et al.*, 2005). Therefore, old age could be described as a period in a man's life

when he cannot adapt appropriately to do what he had been previously adapted to. In this study, old age refers to a period in which a man or female has reached or surpassed 60.

Determinants of Health Challenges Among the Aged Population

Identifying and understanding the drivers of the health challenges of the elderly, whether they are related to conditions and socio-economic inequalities, individual characteristics (biological, psychological, genetic), or behavioural, physical environment, access and use of health services, including cultural and gender differences, are crucial for the development of healthcare policies for the aged population. Fajemilehin and Odebiyi (2011) found in their study, using exploratory, descriptive and cross-sectional study and snowball techniques to purposively select three hundred elderly, 60 years and above, that traditional lifestyles, educational status, having personal money in old age and gender were major drivers of quality life and positive health behaviours among the elderly. This implies that the absence of these drivers can result in poor health among the elderly. The study, which purposively selected ten traditional core health districts in Ife/Ijesa zone of Osun State, Nigeria, found that variations on the influence of other socio-demographic and economic characteristics of the participants, such as living with a spouse, peer relationship, type of marriage and residential location, were significant drivers of health among the elderly. In addition, the study concluded that the elderly traditional lifestyles, educational

background, state of finance, gender and marital stability contributed much to positive health practices and quality of life. As beautiful as the study's findings were, the authors failed to subject their findings to theoretical explanation. Hence, this paper bridges the gap by adequately providing a theoretical framework to understand and assess the drivers for the health challenges of the elderly.

Mojoyinola and Ayangunna (2012) discovered that stability in family contracts and the socio-economic status of the elderly are drivers that account for the possibility that a reciprocity relationship would exist between the elderly and their family members and the ability to purchase needs. Inferentially, these factors are deemed indispensable for enhancing the health status of the old; in their absence, the health status of the elderly is jeopardised. Fajemilehin and Odebiyi (2011) expressed that marital status significantly impacts the health of the elderly because living with a spouse and the type of marriage (be it monogamous or polygynous) promote quality life in old age are relevant for positive health behaviours such as the utilisation of health facilities, using their drugs as prescribed as well as eating and drinking on time in a clean and wholesome environment.

Poverty has also been a driver for health challenges among rural elderly persons (Akpomovie, 2010). Accordingly, poverty in Nigeria is disproportionately distributed across rural and urban areas but higher in the rural and urban fringes than in the urban areas and significantly higher in the Northern part of the country. In a study of the elderly in rural

communities of North Central Nigeria by Adebowale *et al.* (2012), findings revealed that 49.1 percent of the elderly population did not perform well in four measures of well-being, namely, physical, social, psychological and environmental. Accordingly, elderly persons who were married, regularly visited by their children, and who received financial support from their children were less likely to report poor health than those who were lonely and had no financial support. These findings speak volumes for a system that must promote social and economic support for the elderly.

A study conducted by Fonta *et al.* (2017), using multivariate regression analysis in the form of a binary and ordinal logistic regression to determine the association between socioeconomic, demographic and health-related factors among the elderly in Ghana showed that older adults with one or more than one chronic condition were more likely to report poor health. The study, which was conducted among 2,613 elderly persons using data drawn from the World Health Organization's (WHO) Study on global ageing and adult health (SAGE) Wave 1, established that the elderly who rarely engaged in exercise, had never worked in a lifetime and lived with functional limitations and disabilities were more likely to experience health challenges. Also, it was found that respondents in the highest income bracket, former tobacco users and those satisfied with certain aspects of life, respectively, were more likely to report good health. The study concluded that the health of the elderly was in part determined by their birth, upbringing, and lifestyle. The findings indicated that addressing

social challenges at a young age will go a long way toward achieving good health and that people with physical limitations and disabilities are most susceptible to unmet healthcare needs and support systems from the government, policymakers, and family.

Most findings have shown a significant relationship between certain social, economic and demographic drivers affecting the elderly health. French *et al.* (2012) observed that it is important to examine past life experiences, including cultural factors, historical (wars), and national factors (availability of health services), together with individual characteristics when exploring differences in reporting older adults' health. Wang *et al.* (2014), in a study conducted among elderly refugees living in South Korea, found that poor health was related to individuals of low socio-economic statuses, elderly females and those with physical and mental disabilities, including other chronic conditions, owing to past wartime experiences and economic recession. Similarly, Krokstad *et al.* (2002) discovered that individual drivers like low educational attainment increases the chances of reporting poor health among the elderly. A possible pathway could be through lack of employment, low economic condition and consequential inability to take care of healthcare needs. In the same way, socio-cultural drivers impact the quality of health across racial-ethnic groups, owing to the different perceptions of health (Landrine *et al.*, 2016).

In a study conducted by Lindstrom (2019), it was found that being single or divorced increases the chance of reporting poor health among the

elderly owing to emotional instability, loneliness and economic vulnerability. In the same light, the study by Theme-Filha *et al.* (2013) revealed that low income, poor lifestyle choices such as smoking, excessive drinking and lack of exercise are risk factors associated with health challenges among the elderly. A sedentary lifestyle predisposes one to diseases; for instance, smoking increases the chances of dying from medical conditions like ischemic heart disease, lung cancer, stroke and coronary heart disease (Centres for Disease Control and Prevention, CDCP, 2016). Accordingly, physical activity in the form of exercise can reduce the onset of chronic disease and thus improve health outcomes. Some of these health consequences are reversible when the individual is no longer exposed to these poor habits. In terms of physical health, a growing body of evidence relates functional limitations and disabilities to poor health (Landrine *et al.*, 2016; Fonta *et al.*, 2017).

In a study conducted by Ibitoye *et al.* (2015) to examine the psychological well-being of the elderly in Ijumu local government area (LGA) of Kogi State, Nigeria, using a multi-stage sampling technique to select 1,217 elderly aged 65 years and above randomly, findings showed that a higher proportion (53.3%) experienced good psychological well-being. This was associated with age, level of education, current working status and financial assistance from children. The study, which analysed data via descriptive statistics, chi-square tests and binary logistic regression, found that good psychological well-being decreased with increasing age and was lower among those with no education and

primary education compared with their counterparts with secondary education or more. Also, those currently working and receiving financial assistance from children had better psychological well-being. On this note, Dokpesi (2017) claimed that good psychological well-being is threatened by increasing stressors and poor conditions, which also increase the chances of disability, frailty and death.

The WHO (2021) reported that globalisation, technological developments such as transport and communication, urbanisation, migration and changing gender norms are influencing the health status of older adults in both direct and indirect ways. Supportive physical and social environments also enable older people to do what is important to them, despite losses in capacity. The availability of safe and accessible public buildings, transport, and easy walking places are supportive environments. By implication, the lack of these social opportunities and support systems promote poor health among elderly persons. The WHO (2021) noted that developing a public-health response to ageing by strictly focusing on individual and environmental approaches and adaptation increases the drive for psychosocial growth of the aged population to health and well-being.

Health Care Services for the Aged Population Short- and Long-Term Health Care Services

Ageing is associated with functional decline, health and social support needs. Traditionally, the responsibility of providing long-term care and support for older persons has been accepted by

African families. However, modernisation, urbanisation and increased participation of women in the workforce have reduced available primary family caregivers for older adults. Consequently, many families cannot provide long-term care and support for older adults (Cadmus, 2020). According to the WHO (2021), long-term care includes the activities undertaken by others to ensure that individuals at risk of significant loss or with ongoing loss of intrinsic capacity can maintain a functionality consistent with their basic rights, fundamental freedom, and human dignity. Types of long-term care vary and depend on the individual's functional decline and disability (Cadmus, 2020).

With the rising prevalence of chronic diseases, the health system in Africa is less prepared to meet the healthcare needs of the elderly, with little infrastructure and few specialised personnel for older populations (Fonta *et al.*, 2017). Accordingly, in terms of health access, most elderly persons with poor health use health facilities provided by the National Health Insurance policy, which offers free healthcare to elderly persons above 70. While this is seen as a positive development at the national level, the quality of services rendered is not encouraging, and the range of services offered is limited. An inference from this review is that older adults are still valued, but caregivers could be stressed and depreciate the assistance. Developing countries like Nigeria need to consider what types of public care the elderly and their families would need.

Institution-Based and Non-Institution-Based Health Care Services

Institution-based care places the older person in a formalised care setting or arrangement; while non-institution-based care supports the individual within the home or community. However, non-institutionalised long-term care has evolved. Thus seen, the concept of “Aging in Place” focused on the preference of older persons to remain in their homes with care provided at the person's residence without relocation of the individual to a residential facility. However, the definition has grown to include various arrangements, such as retirement communities and assisted living facilities. The concept of “Aging in Place” is particularly relevant in the traditional African setting, where older persons prefer to remain in their homes and familiar environments.

In Nigeria, health services, welfare services and social policies are skewed in favour of young people, especially women and children, thereby leaving the elderly very far behind (Dugarova, 2018). Accordingly, there is no formal social security or welfare for the older population compared to developed countries. The only thing available is a contributory pension scheme such as National Health Insurance Scheme (NHIS) for those who have worked with the government, and their number is relatively small compared to the general population. Nigerian society, however, like many other developing nations, has paid little or no attention to this sub-group due to a lack of a formal structure of care and social support networks (Fajemilehin and Odebiyi, 2011). As a result, the world of older

people largely depends on the informal, traditional family support systems, which have weakened today, although many older adults in Nigeria continue to rely on their children for financial support to meet their daily needs.

Traditionally, older persons in Nigeria were known to enjoy informal social support from close family relations like spouses, children, daughters-in-law and sons-in-law. These forms of support are fading due to the rural-urban migration of youngsters, changes in family structure, increasing unemployment, the rising cost of living and shrinking income (Dugarova, 2018). This corroborates the assertion of the Report by the United Nations, which says, “with increased population mobility and urbanisation, as well as fewer intergenerational households, the provision of household-based social support is becoming more challenging” (UN, 2017 cited in Dugarova, 2018, p. 14). In Shanghai and Beijing, privately run elderly-care institutions account for more than 80 per cent of the total elderly-care institutions, higher than what is obtainable in Nigeria. In China, there were more than 170,000 elderly-care institutions and facilities, with more than half of the institutions privately run nationwide to improve the quality of elderly-care services through adequate funding (Nigerian Newspaper, 2019).

A study conducted by Peil et al. (2019) to examine the support that elderly Nigerians get in the form of services from family, relatives and non-relatives and the effect of their age, sex, location (urban/rural) and state of health on the provision of these services, revealed that children are by far the most important source of assistance,

followed by grandchildren. Furthermore, few older adults were found to have neither children or grandchildren available to help them. However, the study failed to note that increasing levels of migration may also deprive older adults of their children's services and some move to get the care they need. Mascitelli *et al.* (2016) buttressed that women enjoyed more social support through care giving from grandchildren and their engagement in some form of petty trading which makes them live longer. However, peer relationships remain the source of healthy living for the elderly male group.

Global Organisations and the Provision of Healthcare Services for the Elderly

The challenges of the elderly have drawn the world's attention, leading to better policies for them. In 1971, the United Nations General Assembly adopted Resolution 2842, which for the first time in history, asked the Secretary-General and Member States to take concrete action on ageing and the position of older adults in society. First World Assembly on Ageing in Vienna (1984) adopted the International Plan of Action to help the ageing population. In 1991, the UN Principles on Older Persons were formulated to ensure elderly autonomy, participation, care, self-fulfilment, and dignity. As demographics changed, especially in developed countries, so did guidelines, goals, and action plans. The Second World Assembly on Ageing in April 2002 adopted the Madrid International Plan of Action on Ageing and Political Declaration aimed at building a society for all ages. National and international actions in three priority directions

were defined to reach this goal: older persons and development of improved health; well-being in older age; enabling and supportive environment. The WHO (2021) has also championed efforts to address elderly health challenges by creating a Global Strategy and Action Plan for Ageing and Health for 2016–2020 through increased budgetary allocation and development partner involvement, aimed to give everyone a chance to live a long, healthy life.

The United Nations General Assembly declared 2021–2030 the Decade of Healthy Ageing and asked the WHO (2021) to lead the implementation. The Decade of Healthy Ageing is a global collaboration bringing together governments, civil societies, international agencies, professionals, academia, the media and the private sector for ten years of concerted, catalytic and collaborative action to foster longer and healthier lives. The Decade builds on the WHO Global Strategy and Action Plan and the United Nations Madrid International Plan of Action on Ageing by supporting the realisation of the United Nations Agenda 2030 on Sustainable Development and the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs). The Decade of Healthy Ageing (2021–2030) seeks to reduce health inequities and improve the lives of older adults, their families and communities through collective action in four areas: changing how people think, feel and act towards age and ageism; developing communities in ways that foster the abilities of older adults; delivering person-centred integrated care and primary health services responsive to older adults; and providing more senior people who need it with access to quality long-term care.

This is one of the strategies instituted to ensure that elderly persons are adequately cared for.

Nigeria participated in the 2002 African Union Conferences on an action plan for the ageing population, although the country has no formal social security or policy for the ageing population besides the pension scheme for retirees of government employees (Adebowale *et al.*, 2012; Animasahun and Chapman, 2017). Adebowale *et al.* (2012) asserted that Nigeria is currently overhauling its systems towards a robust policy that would protect the dignity of older persons and promote their inclusion, participation, independence, and security. Slow as it may be, there may be a ray of hope for the ageing Nigerian population. The SDGs 2030 Agenda is also one global tool that seeks to address the problem of social exclusion of the vulnerable, including the elderly. It could prove beneficial to the elderly Nigerian population if stakeholders make concerted efforts that are elderly-friendly. The 2030 agenda thus proposes an all-inclusive and sustainable future that “leaves no one behind” in its industrialisation, production, education, poverty reduction, skill transfer and social cohesion strategies.

Federal Government, Health Policies and the Problems of Healthcare Services

The absence of social security systems is detrimental to catering for the needs of the elderly. The studies by Mudiare (2013) and Oladeji (2011) revealed that adequate provision of social services, such as income security, healthcare, housing and legal assistance, positively influences the overall health of the

elderly, but, national social security is unavailable to provide an economic buffer in older age. Accordingly, in 1989, the Nigerian government developed the National Social Development Policy, which aimed to provide a framework for protecting elderly persons from moral and material neglect and provide public assistance when necessary. Despite adequate provisions, however, there has been no effective execution by any Federal agency (Oladeji, 2011). In addition, although regional levels have demonstrated the presence of policy frameworks for the elderly, policy changes have not been observed in Nigeria (Mudiare, 2013). The failure of the Nigerian Federal institutions to regularly disburse pension funds to retirees and provide adequate social services for the aged pose a significant threat to food security, social security and national security.

Nigeria's already inadequately funded healthcare system has placed little emphasis on the care of older adults because there are "more urgent" health problems, thus, funding for older adults is limited (Olayiwola *et al.*, 2013). The healthcare system in Nigeria spends a small fraction of the budget on treating the elderly, and their access to care is severely limited by the paucity of health facilities, human resources, and out-of-pocket payment arrangements (Animasahun and Chapman, 2017). This also occurs against the backdrop of Nigeria not yet enacting the National Policy on the care and welfare of older persons, which has remained in draft form since March 2003. In Nigeria today, social security policies and insurance schemes for the aged are not adequately formulated and

implemented, owing to their failure to cover many older persons or address many of their challenges. Take, for instance, some security systems policies for the elderly cover only the formal sector (public and organised private sector) and are fraught with problems of implementation (Animasahun and Chapman, 2017).

Furthermore, Nigerian Federal institutions fail to regularly disburse pension funds to retirees and provide adequate social services for the aged (Gesinde *et al.*, 2011). In Nigeria, the burden of care squarely rests on family members despite the provisions in the 1999 Constitution, Section 14. 2(b), which states that; "The security and welfare of its people shall be the primary purpose of the government", and in Section 16, subsection 2(d), which promises; "That suitable and adequate shelter and suitable and adequate food, a reasonable national minimum living wage, old age care and pensions and unemployment, sick benefits and welfare of the disabled are provided for all citizens" (The Federal Republic of Nigeria, 1999). The Nigeria Federal Executive Council ratified the National Policy on Ageing for Older Persons in 2021 to adequately address the challenges, including insecurity, independence, and disabilities, among others, associated with old age (Agency Report, 2019). However, the ratification is yet to address the health challenges faced by the elderly in the country.

Similarly, the Federal Ministry of Health attempted to establish six regional geriatric centres in tertiary hospitals to improve older adults' health. The centres were intended to meet

the health and social requirements, as well as the developmental difficulties, of the aged in the country. This project shows that Nigeria's elderly face health challenges that require a strategic approach to promote healthy ageing. The government, the private sector in the Diaspora, a coalition of the elderly, and the formation of the National Senior Citizens Centre were advocated collectively (Agency Report, 2019). Establishing such a centre was seen as an effective strategy to substantially address some of the problems of older persons in Nigeria. Again, the Nigerian President, Muhammad Buhari, had approved the allocation of one per cent of the Consolidated Revenue Fund to deliver healthcare to the vulnerable population, mainly children, women and the elderly (Agency Report, 2019). Accordingly, 50 per cent of the fund would go to the NHIS to procure health services and insurance for vulnerable groups and 45 per cent to the National Primary Health Care Development Agency for the training of the healthcare workforce and procurement of consumables for day-to-day activities of the primary health care centres, while 5 per cent is for health emergencies at the Federal Ministry of Health.

State Governments, Organisations and the Provision of Healthcare Services for the Elderly

Some state government services, as well as some religious organisations, non-governmental organisations and community-based organisations, form the bulk of the network of support for the elderly in Nigeria in addition to the informal arrangement through the family system.

Gesinde *et al.* (2011) noted that some activities had been implemented in the areas of livelihood support, skills acquisition, capacity building, and medical care for the elderly in states like Ekiti and Lagos. There is no regulatory framework for institutionalised elderly care in Nigeria. However, a few states have introduced social assistance for older persons, including Ekiti and Anambra States (Gesinde *et al.*, 2011). Accordingly, these states run social welfare packages for senior citizens aimed at taking care of older adults of 65 years and above in the case of Ekiti State and 75 years and above in the case of Anambra State. The scheme in Ekiti formally took off in 2011, while that of Anambra took off in 2012. In Nigeria, institutions such as old people's homes for the aged are not very common. There are presently few registered privately owned older adults' homes in Nigeria, showing the limited extent of government participation in caring for older adults.

Obinna (2021) noted that it is no longer news that healthcare in Nigeria is not where it should be, particularly the worsening situation of the elderly. He reported that the University Teaching Hospital, Benin, (UBTH), had pioneered ways to provide better care for older adults, discovered better therapies, and educated the next generation of medical professionals, caregivers and community members on the needs of the elderly. The hospital now operates a Geriatric Unit under its Elder-Friendly Hospitals Initiative (ELDRHI), solely dedicated to caring for elderly Nigerians. Geriatrics or geriatric medicine is a speciality that focuses on the health care of older adults, aimed to promote health by preventing

and treating diseases and disabilities in older adults. The unit is strengthened to provide patient-centred, holistic care to older persons in a good ambience that encourages family participation. It manages various categories of patients with geriatric syndromes who otherwise would have required care in other climes. Also provided by the hospital are wheelchair-accessible toilets, handrails and grab bars across the hospital to improve patients' safety.

The Judicial System and the Care for the Elderly

Nigeria's judicial framework has not established a justice mechanism for older adults to seek redress in Nigeria (Age Nigeria Foundation, 2021). Accordingly, some network friends, NGOs and Civil Society Organizations have been at the forefront of fighting against elder abuse and other forms of discrimination and violence against older Nigerians. It has been observed that lawmakers have not been sensitive to the scope, nature and seriousness of older persons' plight in Nigeria; neither are they susceptible to the broad economic and social development implications of leaving these problems unaddressed in the context of rapid population ageing (Olayiwola *et al.*, 2013).

Elder abuse, violence and mistreatment are now on the high side in Nigeria compared to other developed countries, fuelled by a lack of specific laws to protect the elderly (Mudiare, 2013). Accordingly, most elderly persons claimed that negative attitude towards their age was a problem in accessing justice, and this has contributed to the discrimination and abuse they face daily. The

older adults believe that due to their old age, they have less chance to get justice as their complaints are usually not taken seriously. Even in courts, they are treated disrespectfully by court officials or harassed by police. Some older adults believe that court proceedings were designed to exhaust them, or they would die before the matter would be resolved. The financial burden is a significant barrier for older adults trying to access justice in Nigeria, particularly for those who do not earn regular income. Some do not have money to pay lawyers, while some think they cannot pay corrupt officials (Age Nigeria Foundation, 2021).

The specific barriers older adults face regarding access to justice are not adequately covered under International Human Rights law. Older adults are easily discriminated against and are prone to mistreatment, violence and neglect. Most older Nigerians who are victims of elder abuse and mistreatment have judicial problems and are not protected by the legal system, making them more vulnerable to abuse and loss of their possessions, land, properties and houses (Mudiare, 2013). The problem in getting justice is problematic for the elderly in Nigeria, influencing the older adults to clamour for a solution to their justice challenges. Cases like theft and debt, family dispute, divorce, taking another wife and inheritance, unfair dismissal, insurance claims, and scams are challenges older adults find hard to resolve through the judicial process in Nigeria. It is thus seen alternative dispute resolution in Nigeria, like Citizen Mediation Centres, is not well disposed toward granting access to older adults in our society.

Roles of NGOs in the Provision of Healthcare Services

Okah (2021) reported that several non-governmental organisations had taken the challenge of the elderly as their priority. One such NGO is the National Senior Citizens Centre (NSCC) in Nigeria, which planned to engage 14.9 million older adults (statistics from the National Bureau of Statistics in 2019 in Nigeria) to be economically productive in their communities. The objectives of the NSCC were to ensure the provision of programmes and services and accessibility and provide health, social programmes, entrepreneurship, work schemes, and educational as well as living opportunities to older adults. The organisation leveraged existing structures like the Legal Aid Council of Nigeria, Primary Healthcare facilities, the National Orientation Agency, the National Social Safety Net Office, Ministries of Humanitarian Affairs, Health, Agriculture and Rural Development and many others to engage the elderly citizens. The mission of the organisation was to give the elderly opportunities to continue to contribute their wealth of experience to develop their communities. The traditional belief is that people are no longer helpful when they retire. However, the truth is that these retirees possess all their institutional memories, expertise and goodwill acquired over the years, which can be helpful for community development.

Theoretical Framework: Political Economy Theory

The Political Economy Theory is a social science theory concerned with production, trade, and

their relationship with the law and the government. It is interested in how economic theories affect different socio-economic systems, such as socialism and communism, and public policy creation and implementation. Historically, the theory can be traced to scholars like Adam Smith, Karl Marx, David Ricardo, John Stuart Mill, David Hume, and Francois Quesnay, among others. Importantly, the theory studies the interaction between politics and economics. Politics deals with power, authority, public life, governance, the state and conflict resolution. Politics has been defined as all those activities and institutions related to making authoritative societal decisions. Economics has been described as a way of thinking about the provision of material goods, institutions of private property and contracts, or the institutional reality of a market economy. In its basic form, economics deals with how resources and benefits are generated and distributed in society. Therefore, economists seek to understand the self-organising forces of the market economy, how well they function and how governments may intervene to improve their workings in specific situations.

Economics is popularly known as the science that studies human behaviour as a relationship between ends and scarce means with alternative uses. Therefore, if economics is the study of the optimal use of scarce resources, the political economy begins with the political nature of decision-making and is concerned with how politics will affect economic choices in society. The political economy goes beyond simple economics to include social and

institutional processes through which economic and political elites allocate resources for their benefit and then to the broader population. It deals with ways in which politics determines or influences economic activities; how financial circumstances and institutions determine or affect political institutions and processes. It is premised on the idea that politics and the economy cannot be separated. In turn, politics is profoundly shaped by economic relations and economic power and vice versa. Those researching political economy, therefore, investigate the association of politics with the economy, understanding that the economy is already political in its origins and consequences.

Political economics is split into Classical Political Economy and Modern Political Economy. Classical Political Economy is concerned with the works of philosophers such as Niccolo Machiavelli, Adam Smith, and Karl Marx. At the same time, Modern Political Economy is traced to the results of modern philosophers, economists, and political scientists such as John Maynard Keynes, Milton Freidman and Friedrich Hayek. Game Theory influenced Political Economy Theory, as it involves different groups competing for finite resources and power that assesses which policies will provide the most beneficial results. It also relates to the capability of the economy to achieve the desired results. Political Economy theorists are interested in the gains and losses incurred by implementing a certain policy. It gives them an idea of which groups support the policy and which do not. They also examine how individuals increase their utility by participating in political activity.

Capital and labour are used to influence political processes and generate policy outcomes with the most benefit.

For this study, the political economy theory is concerned with how political and economic domains interact and shape individual and population health outcomes, particularly the health of elderly persons. Widdig *et al.* (2022) claimed that elderly persons from an economy increasingly characterised by low-wage, precarious employment, ever-expanding inequality, and a political process that corporations and the wealthy unduly influence will face adverse health consequences. These drives will manifest various health challenges, including hypertension, cataract, arthritis, depression, and dementia. These health challenges can be prevented or swiftly addressed in a country where priority is given to the ageing population's health. Government at all levels can, therefore, make decisions about how best to allocate scarce resources to improve the ageing population's health. In return, healthcare services can be accessible and affordable to elderly persons. Widdig *et al.* (2022) claimed that healthcare services are often unavailable, inaccessible and unaffordable to the majority in developing countries. Accordingly, the health challenges of the elderly are worse in developing countries like Nigeria than in developed nations due to fragility, conflicts, scarcity of financial resources, rudimentary or damaged health infrastructure and limited government stewardship. These, of course, can determine or affect the health-seeking behaviours of the elderly and as well for the basis of chosen coping

strategies to avert the wrath of health problems associated with old age.

Conclusion and Recommendations

It can be concluded that some of the differences in the health of older adults are due to genetics; the majority are the result of people's physical and social environments, such as their homes, neighbourhoods, and communities, as well as their characteristics, such as their sex, ethnicity, or socio-economic status. The settings that people live in as children or even as developing foetuses, combined with their characteristics, have long-term effects on how they age. Physical and social environments can affect health directly or through barriers or incentives that affect opportunities, decisions and health behaviour. This paper also noted that the available healthcare services for the elderly are insufficient to cater to their needs. Notably, the families remain the primary caregivers even though some are no longer playing their roles as traditionally expected due to several factors, including industrialisation, urbanisation, unemployment, poverty and poor policies.

Additionally, older adults are sometimes starved when their caregivers are absent due to a lack of provision or problems encountered in day-to-day interactions. The public services are also not drafted to cater for the needs of the elderly, and when drafted, they rarely take care of the challenges faced by the elderly in society. Nigeria's policy leaves older adults in the hands of informal caregivers who may not have adequate medical and social requisites to take good care of them. Maintaining healthy behaviours

throughout life, mainly eating a balanced diet, engaging in regular physical activity, improving physical and mental capacity, delaying care dependency and refraining from tobacco use, all contribute to reducing the risk of non-communicable diseases. The study suggests that the health of the elderly is in part determined by their birth, upbringing, and lifestyle. The findings suggest that addressing social challenges faced by young people will contribute significantly to achieving good health in old age. Also, older adults with physical limitations and disabilities are most susceptible to unmet healthcare needs and support systems from the government, policymakers and family. Therefore, stakeholders should prioritise the health of the elderly for optimal societal development.

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